

Photonic Time Crystals and the Physics of Temporal Periodicity

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Abstract

Photonic Time Crystals (PTCs) are a recently emerging class of optical media whose refractive index varies periodically in time, rather than in space. Building on the broader theoretical foundation of time crystals, PTCs have attracted growing attention for their ability to host unique physical phenomena such as photonic bandgaps in the time domain, temporal reflections, nonreciprocal light propagation, and topological effects in the time domain. This review provides a comprehensive survey of the field, tracing its evolution from Wilczek's original proposal of time-translation symmetry breaking to current realizations of temporal photonic media. We examine the theoretical formalism underpinning PTCs, recent experimental breakthroughs, and emerging application areas including Floquet photonics, ultrafast modulation, and temporal metasurfaces. Along synthesizing existing literature, we highlight open questions and discuss the theoretical and practical frontiers of PTCs in the context of optical computing, time-varying metamaterials, and dynamically reconfigurable photonic systems.

1. Introduction

Photonic time crystals (PTCs) are optical systems whose electromagnetic properties vary periodically in time, enabling wave phenomena that do not occur in spatially periodic materials. PTCs work by abrupt, periodic modulation of the refractive index in time, which creates temporal analogues of refraction and reflection. These systems represent a burgeoning subfield within time-crystal research. Over the past decade, this concept has grown from a theoretical extension of time-translation symmetry breaking into a rapidly advancing area of photonics with distinct mechanisms and potential applications. The aim of this report is to provide a clear overview of the field for scientists outside this speciality. Our discussion begins with the physical background and early theoretical developments that motivated the study of time-periodic media. It then traces the progression of research leading to modern formulations of PTCs. The main body of this report examines recent advances from the past three years, highlighting key results and areas of active investigation. The report concludes with a synthesis of current understanding, outstanding challenges, and possible future direction.

This paper is organized into different sections as follows: Section 2 gives a brief review of all the papers studied for this report. Section 3 introduces the historical and theoretical background of time crystals, beginning with Wilczek's foundational proposal and tracing the shift toward non-equilibrium and classical time-crystalline systems. Section 4 outlines the development of photonic time crystals (PTCs) from these early concepts, leading to their realization in optical platforms. Section 5 explores the core physical properties of PTCs, including Floquet-Bloch states, momentum bandgaps, and topological effects in

the time domain. Section 6 reviews current research in the field, covering key theoretical and experimental advances such as light amplification, photon pair creation, and metasurface-based implementations. Section 7 discusses future applications and technical challenges, emphasizing potential roles of PTCs in optical computing, quantum light sources, and programmable nanophotonic systems. Section 8 presents the conclusion, synthesizing insights across the paper and outlining open questions for future investigation.

2. Literature Review

The concept of time crystals was introduced by Frank Wilczek in 2012, who proposed that certain systems could spontaneously break time-translation symmetry, leading to periodic motion in the ground state [1]. However, Watanabe and Oshikawa rigorously proved that such behavior is impossible in equilibrium systems governed by short-range interactions, effectively ruling out time crystals in static, closed quantum systems [2].

This led to a major shift in the field, as researchers began exploring non-equilibrium and periodically driven systems instead. These so-called discrete (or Floquet) time crystals rely on periodic external drives and mechanisms such as many-body localization to prevent thermalization and support stable, long-lived oscillatory states [3]. Foundational theoretical models were soon followed by experimental demonstrations in systems such as trapped ions [8], ultracold atoms [6], and disordered spin chains [7]. A broad summary of the first decade of time-crystal research is provided in a recent review by Hannaford and Sacha [5].

As the field matured, a parallel effort emerged to extend time-crystalline concepts to classical and photonic systems. Wilczek and Shapere argued that classical dynamical systems can also exhibit spontaneous time symmetry breaking, laying the conceptual groundwork for photonic time crystals (PTCs) [4]. These systems leverage periodic temporal modulation of material parameters, such as refractive index, to manipulate light in ways unattainable with static media.

Recent work has shown that PTCs support phenomena like temporal bandgaps, Floquet-Bloch modes, nonreciprocal propagation, and even topologically protected states [10]. Experimental advances include meta-surface-based PTCs [13], optical implementations of the dynamical Casimir effect [12], and wave amplification via temporal modulation [14,15]. Meanwhile, researchers have explored the analogies and overlaps between PTCs and related platforms like time-varying Mie resonators [18] and inverse-designed nanophotonic structures [19]. These connections highlight a broader movement in

photonics toward active temporal control of material properties as a tool for wave manipulation.

Despite these advances, challenges remain in scaling PTC behavior to optical frequencies due to limitations in ultrafast modulation and material dispersion [11]. Nonetheless, the growing body of literature—including quantum-emitter studies [17,20] and dissipative optical time crystals [16]—indicates that PTCs are rapidly becoming a versatile and foundational platform in modern photonics.

3. Conception of Time Crystals

The modern understanding of time crystals begins with Wilczek's 2012 proposal that a ground-state system could spontaneously break time-translation symmetry by exhibiting periodic change, specifically motion, in time. The idea was motivated by the question of whether time translation symmetry, normally assumed fundamental, could be broken in analogy to spatial-translation symmetry in ordinary crystals. Using a model that involved a charged particle on a ring threaded by magnetic flux, Wilczek argued that spontaneous time symmetry breaking required a macroscopically distinguishable ground state (lowest energy & observable (exist and are distinguishable by an external observer)) and infinitely many degrees of freedom (influenced at every point in space and time, like an infinite crystal or superconductor) to prevent tunnelling between degenerate configurations. Based on these conditions, he constructed a soliton-like model - a stable, self-reinforcing wave packet - whose constant-energy motion would simultaneously break spatial and temporal translation symmetry [1].

Shortly afterward, Watanabe and Oshikawa examined these claims and showed that equilibrium time crystals cannot arise in systems governed by short-range Hamiltonians. By introducing a rigorous mathematical definition of time crystals through time-dependent correlation functions, they demonstrated the absence of long-range temporal order at both zero and finite temperatures. Through manipulation of formulae created, it became evident that apparent time-dependent work in condensates is not physically observable when particle number is strictly conserved, meaning such systems cannot serve as true time crystals. They concluded that equilibrium time crystals are impossible because temporal and spatial symmetry breaking behave fundamentally differently in equilibrium [2].

As Wilczek's original idea was shown to be invalid by Watanabe and Oshikawa, the field of time crystals had to be reimaged. A review article involving Wilczek summarized this shift within the field toward non-equilibrium systems, introducing the framework of

discrete time crystals in periodically driven many-body systems. These systems rely on mechanisms such as many-body localization or long-lived prethermal states to avoid thermalization, allowing persistent or exponentially long-lived periodic responses in time. Experiments on periodically-driven platforms including trapped ions, artificial atoms, and nuclear spins confirmed that such systems can exhibit stable time-crystalline behaviour under conditions of weak disorder, long-range interactions, and strong isolation from the environment. This reformulation established multiple realizable types of time crystals, including classical or open-system variants closely linked to the conceptual foundations underlying PTCs [3].

Furthermore, the subfield, classical time crystals, that photonic time crystals belong to, was first inspired by a separate paper by Wilczek and Shapere. In this paper, they proposed that classical (not just quantum) dynamical systems can spontaneously break time-translation symmetry, meaning that their lowest energy states would exhibit persistent periodic motion – analogous to how atoms form a spatial crystal by breaking spatial translational symmetry. This led to experimental proposals – including those in photonic systems – where large and robust time crystalline states might have technological applications [4].

4. Development and Progression from Time Crystals to PTCs

Although the background expounded is insightful for the field's history, review article [5] sheds light on the steps thereafter up to and including 2022 that led to the inception of PTCs.

Revitalization of the field occurred in the early 2010s where quantum time crystals were devised from closed but periodically driven system, dubbed as discrete or Floquet time crystals. This drive defined the crystals is an external, periodic force applied to a system to make it behave like a crystal in time. Realizations of these crystals first occurred in 2015, where ultra-cold atoms were shown to reorganize themselves with time [5]. Sacha's 2015 paper proposes an experiment where ultra-cold atoms (forming a Bose-Einstein condensate) bounce on a periodically oscillating mirror, under gravity. When the mirror's driving period is T , due to atomic interactions and certain resonance conditions, the atomic cloud reorganizes so that the motion becomes periodic with period $2T$, called period doubling – i.e., the atoms evolve with a period double the drive, a hallmark of discrete time crystal behavior. This outcome is explained by the spontaneous breaking of time-translation symmetry – atoms start in a state that follows the external drive period, but under weak perturbations (such as atom loss or measurements), the system transitions to a state oscillating at double the drive period [6].

Smith et. al. in 2016 detailed theoretical developments showing that time crystal phases – where a system’s behavior repeats after an integer multiple of the driving period, breaking discrete time-translation symmetry – can be realized in periodically driven spin chains in solid-state systems. These systems are engineered to have spins that are flipped periodically via external driving (Floquet engineering). Through many-body interactions and disorder, the spins can lock into a state where oscillations persist at a period longer than drive – period doubling, which is the hallmark of a discrete time crystal [7]. These theoretical proposals from 2016 set the stage for subsequent experimental realizations (in 2017), such as using trapped ions and nitrogen-vacancy centers in diamond, that aimed to explore their potential applications in quantum technologies. This established the basic protocol of periodically flipping spins in a solid-state context to achieve robust time-crystalline phases.

Zhang et. al., in their 2017 study, confirms the first direct experimental observation of a discrete time crystal phase in a spin chain of trapped atomic ions. The experiment applies a periodic sequence of Hamiltonians to ten interacting spins with long-range sling interactions (a type of spin coupling) and controllable disorder. When all conditions (such as periodic drive, spin-spin interactions, disorder, etc.) are present, the spin system exhibits robust oscillations in magnetization at a period twice (or in some studies even thrice) that of the driving frequency [8]. Thus, discrete time crystals can be realized in spin-based quantum systems and provides a blueprint for subsequent experiments with spins and ultra-cold atoms, which showed similar results.

The possibility of realizing time-crystalline behavior in systems governed by time-independent equations was first demonstrated in 2019, providing a route toward implementations reminiscent of Wilczek’s original proposal. Subsequent work focused on dissipative time crystals, described by thermodynamic or Lindblad-type equations that admit non-equilibrium steady states which spontaneously break time-translation symmetry and exhibit persistent periodic evolution. In this framework, systems such as Bose–Einstein condensates and grand canonical ensembles can display time-crystalline behavior despite the absence of explicit time dependence in their governing dynamics [5].

While these results appear to contradict the no-go theorem established by Watanabe and Oshikawa, they do not invalidate it. Instead, they operate outside its domain of applicability by abandoning the assumption of closed, equilibrium dynamics. The emergence of time-periodic steady states in dissipative or open systems is therefore consistent with, and in fact reinforces, the conceptual boundaries identified in earlier work [2].

However, majority of these experiments were conducted for ultra-cold atoms. Instead, for optical systems, researchers theoretically realized that big discrete time crystals that can live forever without the stringent requirement that other time crystals needed. These experiments could be constructed at room temperature, without advanced equipment, allowing for a direct and straightforward translation to the real world (where time crystals could allow for optical quantum computers, precise clocks, optical amplification). From these optical experiments, PTCs were realized. Although they were not spontaneous and needed externally imposed fabrication of refractive indices, they were borne from the extensive history of this field [5].

Not only were PTCs realized, but certain ideas for time crystals were studied in photonic ones. For example, PTCs were studied with temporal Anderson localization (disorder traps itself into one small region with that wavefunction decaying exponentially away from that small point) was shown to decay in time, creating temporal disorder [9].

5. Properties of PTCs

With the historical aspect of PTCs explored, its properties need to be fully established. For PTCs, its time-periodicity produces Floquet-Bloch states (quantum or classical wave states that arise when a system experiences periodic modulation in space (Bloch) and/or time (Floquet)) and momentum band gaps (where waves do not pass through), giving PTCs a unique wave propagation behavior. PTCs can host topologically non-trivial phases, characterized by invariants such as the Zak phase (geometric phase acquired by a wavefunction as it traverses the Brillouin zone of a one-dimensional periodic system). These topological phases lead to robust temporal edge states, which localize energy in time rather than space. Advances in ultrafast materials (e.g., epsilon-near-zero metamaterials) make these effects experimentally feasible at optical frequencies. The combination of temporal periodicity and topology positions PTCs as an emerging platform for novel wave-control mechanisms [10].

A key property of PTCs is its ability to amplify light through their periodic variations in time. This occurs due electron interactions with the Floquet modes in the momentum gaps, where the radiation it emits can be exponentially amplified. This draws energy directly from the time modulation.

Early theoretical predictions of PTCs often leaned on spatial-temporal analogies envisioning dramatic phenomena from momentum bandgaps to time reversal of light. However, real world materials are fundamentally related by how quickly they can change, a property known as temporal dispersion. Practically, this means generating

strong time-dependent effects in the optical domain which requires exceptionally fast and energetic modulation which is far beyond what ordinary materials and standard experimental setups can provide. Furthermore, such demanding conditions obscure PTC effects with more familiar nonlinear responses, complicating experimental demonstration [11].

6. Current Research on PTCs

Using the general history and conceptual framework of time crystals established, current research of PTCs is anchored within its field and can now be discussed. Such work focuses on the practical applications and realizations of the PTC.

In their theoretical paper, Sustaeta-Osuna et. Al. describes that when PTCs amplify light, the crystals create correlated photon pairs from a vacuum. This is the dynamical Casimir effect, where quantum fluctuations result in real photons by tailoring how the medium changes in time and controlling vacuum amplification. They also wrestle with this effect within the complex variables of PTCs, which is treated fully analytically as pair generation arises only by a few temporal boundaries. Using a mathematical framework and analytical approaches, they conceived PTCs that had its refractive index switch between two values. The paper showed how light behaved as a switch, showing momentum band gaps and exponential wave amplification (via vacuum amplification and squeezing). Simultaneously they studied the quantum structure of PTCs for photon pair creation, which was affected by the PTCs squeezing.

This demonstrated a link between the classical (bandgaps and wave amplification) and quantum (photon pair creation) elements, showing that the physics that amplifies light also makes photons appear. Reflectivity was used to determine the squeezing strength of the PTCs, which also controlled photon creation. The momentum bandgaps corresponded to the exponential growth of light intensity and the Casimir effect which led to vacuum amplification [12].

One limitation of synthesising PTCs is its difficulty to do so in 3D states, due to its need for uniform modulation in volumetric samples. In their 2023 experimental paper, Wang et. al. extends the concept of PTCs to artificial 2D structures, called meta surfaces. These preserve the physical properties of volumetric PTCs even with simpler topology like exponential wave amplification within common momentum bandgaps. Such a reconfiguration of PTCs using meta surfaces at microwave frequency provides a straightforward and realistic method for amplification that could be used for future wireless communication. The method used was to design a theoretical meta surface with

features such as surface impedance or periodically modulating capacitance, then model it by simulating band structure which showed that it would be time periodic. Finally, they experimentally fabricated it, showing that it could modulate at different frequencies and when exciting surface waves, they measured the output power spectrum. Hence, meta surfaces amplify waves with observable band gaps showing that 2D structures can be PTCs as well. Wang and his colleagues proved exponential amplification of waves and showed the practical and versatile realizations of PTCs [13].

Dikopoltsev et. al. in their paper investigate how a free electron moving in a PTC spontaneously emits radiation. Which leads to radiation amplification (as described above). The study explores how both classical and quantum effects yield new forms of radiation, including regions where the electron velocity is both below and above the Cherenkov threshold – demonstrating emission even in cases where traditional Cherenkov radiation is forbidden. Simulations and analytical modelling confirm that this emission can be highly directional, tunable and strongly affected by the temporal modulation of the medium. Their results have direct applications for creating new types of particle detectors and studying quantum correlations and relativistic effects in moving dipoles. It also establishes PTCs as fundamentally different from ordinary photonic crystals, especially in their interactions with free electrons and in their emission properties [14].

PTCs can exponentially amplify light emission from a point source (such as an atom or a quantum dot embedded within the crystal) due to modes associated with the momentum bandgap. Unlike spatial photonic crystals (SPCs) which conserve energy, PTCs draw energy from the external modulation, leading to exponential growth of electromagnetic fields in the gap modes. The amplification is maximized at the middle of the momentum bandgap – enabling non-resonant, tunable laser action without traditional resonance requirements. The growth rate and emission spectrum are strongly controlled by the modulation amplitude, making PTCs a platform for engineered light amplification and highly flexible lasing. This reveals a fundamentally new pathway for lasing and light amplification by leveraging temporal (rather than spatial) modulation and bandgaps. PTCs can serve not only as new platforms for light manipulation but also as active media for lasing and amplification, drawing energy directly from time modulation [15].

Not only has the realization of PTCs and its behaviors been conceived, but it has itself been used to offshoot new ideas. One of these is realizing all-optical dissipative discrete time crystals. Taheri et. al. in their 2022 paper aim to realize a discrete time crystal using optics (an all-photonic hardware platform, without using ultra-cold atoms or spins) and show that a dissipative system can realistically be an open system time crystal. Their method was to use two lasers to periodically drive nonlinear optical cavity into a

spontaneous new rhythm. Their immediate result was time crystal behavior despite irregularities. Like PTCs, these were all-optical and room temperature, making them more practical. Both this system and photonic time crystals share the same mathematical structure, but here the time-crystalline behavior emerges from light dynamics in an optical resonator, whereas in PTCs the temporal modulation is externally imposed [16].

Park et. al. in their 2025 paper explore how periodic modulation in PTCs impact spontaneous emission processes of quantum emitters. Using classical and Floquet theory, they find that the spontaneous emission decay rate is substantially enhanced at the momentum gap frequency of the PTC – unlike in static or spatially periodic systems. Their study uncovers that PTCs allow a nonequilibrium process where an atom can be spontaneously excited from the ground state while emitting a photon, drawing the required energy from the time modulation. Such effects arise from unique band structure, loss and gain regions, and non-orthogonality of Floquet modes in PTCs. It highlights the need for non-Hermitian and Floquet-based frameworks in analyzing light-matter interactions in PTCs, as conventional Hermitian quantum optics is insufficient. In essence, their work advances our understanding of light-matter interactions in PTCs, proving that temporal modulation enables enhanced and unique emission/excitation processes, thus expanding both the theoretical and practical landscape of PTC research [17].

Mie resonators are nanoscale photonic structures that trap light through interference, producing strong resonances. Traditionally, they have fixed geometries and materials, but recent advances have introduced temporal modulation to dynamically control their optical properties. Both time-varying Mie resonators and photonic time crystals (PTCs) manipulate light using temporal modulation of material properties like dielectric permittivity. While PTCs explore periodic modulation to create temporal bandgaps and time-domain Floquet modes, Mie resonators apply similar principles at the nanoscale to dynamically tune scattering behavior, emission, and quantum interactions. The approach exploits Floquet theory to adjust electromagnetic responses dynamically. Thus, the time-varying Mie resonator paradigm is a nanoscale extension and implementation of the same principles as PTC research. Both realize new regimes of wave control, exploit periodic time modulation for unprecedented tunability in emission and propagation, and open doors to active, adaptable photonic and quantum-integrated systems, Advances in either field directly inform and empower progress in the other [18].

Garg et. al. present an advanced computational approach to design nanophotonic structures whose dielectric properties can be actively modulated in time and engineered for dispersive responses. Using inverse design methods and machine learning techniques, they optimize temporal and spectral properties of nanostructures, enabling new methods

of light manipulation such as tailored frequency conversion, controlled scattering, and dynamic modulation of electromagnetic responses. At their core, both this topic and PTCs explore materials whose properties change with time, not just space. They extend photonics into the time domain – where the evolution of permittivity is engineered deliberately. Just as PTCs utilize periodic time modulation to create temporal bandgaps, amplify/suppress light, and enable new quantum interactions, inverse-designed time-varying nanostructures use computational optimization to realize functional devices that operate on similar temporal control principles. Their research is a computational and practical complement to the theoretical foundations of PTCs, offering real-world routes to fabricate and deploy time modulated nanostructures that can harness and expand on the physics of PTCs. This directly unites temporal material control and photonic device engineering [19].

Ren et. al. provides the theoretical and classical groundwork necessary to accurately model and exploit quantum emitter behavior in actively controlled photonic environments – such as the time-modulated, inverse-designed nanostructures and PTC-inspired devices developed by Garg et. al. Their results reinforce the importance of advanced simulation and accurate emission rate calculation in the emerging field of temporal photonic device engineering [20].

7. Future Applications

As we can see, PTCs have evolved from a speculative extension of time-translational symmetry breaking into a concrete and rapidly developing domain of photonics. Early work in this field established the theoretical foundations by connecting temporal modulation to Floquet physics, temporal bandgaps, and novel forms of wave propagation not supported in static or spatially periodic structures. Over the past several years, experimental realizations have verified key predictions of the field: exponential wave amplification, temporal edge states, photon-pair creation through dynamical Casimir processes, free-electron emission control, and meta surface-based implementations that bring PTCs closer to practical device platforms. Together, these developments position PTCs not merely as a conceptual curiosity, but as an emerging technological framework for engineering light using time as an active degree of freedom.

Despite the progress, the field remains at an early stage. Many of the strongest demonstrations rely on idealized modulation conditions, limited material platforms, or microwave-frequency implementations rather than true optical-scale structures. Future advances will depend on improving ultrafast modulation technologies, reducing dispersion-limited constraints, and developing material systems that can sustain large

refractive-index changes without introducing disruptive nonlinearities or loss. Another key direction is establishing unified theoretical tools that incorporate non-Hermiticity, Floquet mode nonorthogonality, and quantum light-matter interactions. Such frameworks will be essential to accurately model emission, amplification, and squeezing in realistic time-varying media.

A significant frontier lies in extending PTC phenomena beyond one-dimensional temporal modulation toward higher-dimensional and hybrid spatiotemporal structures. Meta surface-based PTCs demonstrate that lower dimensional architectures can mimic volumetric behavior, suggesting a path toward compact, integrated devices. Similarly, free-electron interactions with PTCs and time-varying Mie resonators highlight opportunities for particle-photon coupling, on-chip quantum control, and nanoscale radiation engineering. Inverse-designed time-varying nanostructures may also enable programmable temporal photonics, where dispersion, modulation profiles, and emission pathways are optimized algorithmically rather than manually engineered.

In the long term, PTCs could support a wide range of applications. Their ability to amplify light without traditional resonance requirements suggests new classes of tunable lasers and gain media. Temporal bandgaps and Floquet-engineered emission control may enable ultrafast switches, high-efficiency frequency converters, and dynamically reconfigurable photonic circuits. The connection to quantum optics is equally promising: PTCs provide a natural platform for producing squeezed states, entangled photon pairs, and potentially even room-temperature quantum light sources. Finally, the strong interaction between moving charges and time-modulated media may lead to compact particle detectors and radiation sources with functionalities unavailable in conventional photonic systems.

8. Conclusion

Overall, photonic time crystals represent a growing intersection of condensed-matter concepts, ultrafast photonics, quantum technologies, and computational design. Although many practical challenges remain, the recent surge of experimental and theoretical progress suggests that PTCs will continue to expand both scientifically and technologically. Their unique reliance on time modulation opens avenues for controlling electromagnetic waves that are not accessible through spatial engineering alone, making them a compelling direction for future research in integrated photonics and quantum information science.

This paper has reviewed the theoretical foundations of time crystals, traced their evolution from Wilczek's early proposals to practical photonic realizations, and surveyed key experimental advances and emerging applications. We have also highlighted conceptual overlaps with related platforms such as time-varying Mie resonators and temporally modulated nanophotonic structures, which together form a growing ecosystem of time-domain photonics.

As the field matures, several open questions remain. These include the design of robust temporal interfaces, the interplay between quantum coherence and temporal modulation, and the development of scalable, reconfigurable photonic devices based on PTC principles. Integrating PTCs with quantum emitters, nonlinear media, and adaptive materials offers promising directions for both fundamental discovery and technological innovation.

Ultimately, Photonic Time Crystals invite us to rethink the role of time in optical systems—not merely as a parameter but as an active dimension for engineering light-matter interaction. Continued exploration of this temporal degree of freedom is likely to yield transformative advances in ultrafast optics, quantum photonics, and time-varying metamaterials.

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